

Global Warming

Notes by Robbie Morrison
20 May 1990

Jan Sinclair, an environmental journalist came to our April meeting to tell us about climate change. The small turnout led to a very informative group discussion but many missed the chance to learn more.

OUTLINE

The greenhouse effect takes place in the lower atmosphere where naturally controlled greenhouse gases (mainly CO_2) trap the sun's heat and bring our planet to a habitable temperature. Pouring out industrially produced gases has rapidly intensified this effect.

The ozone layer (O_3) in the upper atmosphere (stratosphere) protects life from excessive UV. Again industrially produced gases deplete this layer (mainly CFC's)

For simplicity (and campaigning) these two effects are often viewed in isolation. However they strongly interact.

For example increasing UV is thought to significantly reduce the CO_2 fixing capacity of plankton from 50% globally to 35%. A deficit of a much needed 15%.

And in the other direction the greenhouse effect will lead to less outgoing heat, a cooler stratosphere and increase ozone depletion.

ACTION

We urgently need to:

- Radically reduce energy waste and use.
- Plant trees for CO_2 uptake, halt deforestation.
- Develop renewable energies including biomass.

IMPACTS

- Sea level rise: 30cm in 40 years, 100cm in 110 years.
- Weather patterns change.
- Agriculture will need to adapt rapidly.
- Health epidemics. Tropical diseases spread
- Skin cancer, Cataracts
- Insect plagues
- Reduced vaccination effectiveness due to UV-B skin exposure.
- Environmental refugees.

FURTHER INFORMATION

GENERAL - Hothouse Earth. John Gribbin. Bantam Press. Hardback £12.95

INCL. ECONOMIC JUSTICE - The New Internationalist Magazine No 206 April 1990 on Global Warming. £1.50 incl postage. Write to New Internationalist, 42 Hythe Bridge Street, Oxford OX1 2EP.

AND watch for the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) report in November 1990.

GRAPHS

Jan showed the following graphs

1

□ Land air temperature since 1850.

ⓐ Decrease in temp 1940-65 thought to be due to industrially produced dust and smog masking global warming

ⓑ This anomaly not present in Southern Hemisphere

ⓒ Combined graph.

CONCLUSION - general warming trend from 1880 onwards.

2

□ Sea level air pressure (SLP) since 1946. North Pacific

Increased retention of solar energy by greenhouse gases may lead to both global temp rise and increasingly violent storms (low pressure events)

CONCLUSION - significant change in major weather systems.

3

□ Snow area decrease since 1970. Northern Hemisphere. Measured by satellite. With global warming, precipitation falls as rain, the snow line rises, and snow area is reduced.

CONCLUSION - significant decrease in snow cover since 1980.

4

□ Air temp and CO₂ concentration during last ice ages.

There have been 8 ice ages during last 1,000,000 years. We are living in a short interglacial. Last ice age terminated 10,000 years ago, previous one 130,000 years ago. Both are clearly visible on the graph.

At the end of an ice age the increase in atmospheric temperature (LINE A) is mirrored by a rise in CO₂ (LINE B). The mechanism is not understood.

Also plotted: LINE C correlates with global ice extent. (see

Scientific American, Jan 1990, p44 for explanation of oxygen isotope measurements in deep sea cores). LINE D shows sea level change recorded by rising coast line in New Guinea. Vostok is in central Antarctica. (see next page)

CONCLUSION (4) - SPECULATIVE - We think ice ages involve a massive reorganisation of the way heat is circulated and stored in the oceans and atmosphere FORCED by variations in the earth's orbit. We are now forcing these same systems by artificially increasing the concentration of CO₂ through industrial activity. This may RESULT in a similar catastrophic reorganisation meaning our climate could flip to another mode with disastrous effect for all life. Some people suggest the ocean current which keeps Britain uncharacteristically warm (the Atlantic conveyor) may shut down and temperatures would ironically drop amidst global warming.

OVERALL

The point is the life support systems that make the planet habitable are complex and ill-understood. Our planet is a strange anomaly. We burn vast areas of forest, we burn carbon buried for millions of years, we impact the life support systems on our enchanting planet AT OUR TOTAL PERIL.

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Action

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Impacts

- Sea level rise : 30cm in 40 years, 100cm in 110 years
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Further information

General : Gribbin, John R (1990). *Hothouse Earth: the greenhouse effect and gaia*. London, United Kingdom: Bantam Press. ISBN 978-0-593-01795-1. Hardback. Price £12.95

Including economic justice : New Internationalist (April 1990). "Global warming: how to turn down the heat — Special issue". *New Internationalist*. (206). ISSN 0305-9529. Price £1.50 including postage. Write to New Internationalist, 42 Hythe Bridge Street, Oxford OX1 2EP.

And watch for the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) report in November 1990 : Houghton, John T, GJ Jenkins, and JJ Ephraums (editors) (November 1990). *Climate change: the IPCC scientific assessment — Report prepared for Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change by Working Group I*. Cambridge, United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press. ISBN 0-152-40720-6. [URL for Digitized PDF].

Graphs

Jan showed the following graphs.

- 1: Land air temperature since 1850
- a: Decrease in temperature 1940–65 thought to be due to industrially produced dust and smog masking global warming
- b: This anomaly is not present in the Southern Hemisphere
- c: Combined graph

Conclusion : General warming trend from 1880 onwards

Diagrams 1a and 1b similar to figure 7.6 (p206) in IPCC FAR WGI report

- 2: Sea level air pressure (SLP) since 1946. North Pacific
- Increased retention of solar energy by greenhouse gasses may lead to both global temp rise and increasingly violent storms (low pressure events)

Conclusion : Significant change in major weather systems

- 3: Snow area decrease since 1970
- Measured by satellite. With global warming precipitation falls as rain, the snow line rises, and snow area is reduced.

Conclusion : significant decrease in snow cover since 1980

Diagram 3 similar to figure 7.19 (p224) in IPCC FAR WGI report

- 4: Air temp and CO₂ concentration during last ice ages
- There have been 8 ice ages during the last 1,000,00 years. We are living in a short interglacial. Last ice age terminated 10,000 years ago, previous one 130,000 years ago. Both are clearly visible on the graph.
- At the end of an ice age the increase in atmospheric temperature (**line A**) is mirrored by a rise in CO₂ (**line B**). The mechanism is not well understood.
- Also plotted: **line C** correlates with global ice extent. (See Scientific American, January 1990, p44 for an explanation of oxygen isotope measurements in deep sea cores.) **line D** shows sea level change recorded by rising coastline in New Guinea. Vostok is in central Antarctica. (see next page)

Conclusion : SPECULATIVE: We think ice ages involve a massive reorganization of the way heat is circulated and stored in the oceans and atmosphere **forced** by variations in the earth's orbit. We are now forcing these same systems by artificially increasing the concentration of CO₂ through industrial activity. This may **result** in a similar catastrophic reorganization. Meaning our climate could flip to another mode with disastrous effects for all life. Some people suggest the ocean current which keeps Britain uncharacteristically warm (the Atlantic conveyor) may shut down and temperatures would ironically drop amidst global warming.

Overall

The point is the life support systems that make the planet habitable are complex and ill-understood. Our planet is a strange anomaly. We burn vast areas of forest, we burn carbon buried for millions of years, we impact our life support systems on our enchanting planet **at our total peril.**

This is happening!

□